

EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY SEAFLOOR AND WATER COLUMN OBSERVATORY IBERIAN MARGIN (EMSO-ERIC)

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY SEAFLOOR AND WATER COLUMN OBSERVATORY IBERIAN MARGIN (EMSO-ERIC) - DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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OBJECTIVE

This document serves as a best practice guideline on how to organize, store, and distribute datasets, collected from the Iberian Margin by all partners of EMSO-ERIC Iberian Margin. Scientists are asked to follow this procedure and harmonize their data accordingly with the below described conventions and standards in order to facilitate data management and sharing on a global scale. Processed and validated (meta)data from all entities of the EMSO-ERIC Iberian Margin should be aggregated by the Data Manager, Sarah A. Rautenbach and subsequently made available openly and free of charge for others.

EMSO-ERIC IBERIAN MARGIN NODE

CENTRO DE CIÊNCIAS DO MAR (CCMAR)

PLATFORM NAME: WIREWALKER, ADCP SUBSURFACE BUOY

DESCRIPTION: Off the shelf platform resulting from two individual systems: A) Wirewalker - wave powered autonomous profiler, equipped with a data-logger continuously sampling from 0 to 150 m depth; B) subsurface buoy, fixed at 150 m, equipped with a top faced ADCP. Both items are moored..

EQUIPMENT: WIREWALKER: RBRmaestro3 CTD, Turner Designs Cyclops-7F fluorometer (turbidity and chlorophyl), RBR Coda T.ODO

ACOUSTIC DOPPLER CURRENT PROFILER (ADCP): Teledyne RDI Sentinel V100 (300 kHz) ADCP

CURRENT STATE: 2nd pilot deployment June 2022 - ongoing

CENTRO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO TECNOLOGIA DO ALGARVE (CINTAL)

PLATFORM NAME: N.A.

DESCRIPTION: Hydrophone, that will be connected to EGIM (IPMA).

EQUIPMENT: Hydrophone

CURRENT STATE: *unkown*

ESTRUTURA DE MISSÃO PARA A EXTENSÃO DA PLATFORMA CONTINENTAL (EMEPC)

PLATFORM NAME: ROV LUSO

DESCRIPTION: Installation of the multibeam and some support equipment at the ROV Luso.

EQUIPMENT: Norbit WBMS Multibeam, N/A/Argus Electric Bottle, Rovins Nano/Ixblue Inertial Navigation System, TI/NKE Instrumentation Temperature data logger

CURRENT STATE: EXPLOSEA 2 Campaign July 2019

FACULDADE DE ENGENHARIA DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (FEUP)

PLATFORM NAME: Autonomous Surface Vehicle (ASV)

DESCRIPTION: AutoNaut's Wave Foil Technology converts energy from the pitch and roll of the hull in waves into thrust. The vessel is propelled forward by four keel-mounted foils. In calm conditions the system can be assisted by an auxiliary propulsor. It has operated consistently in conditions of; Sea-state 6.3 m waves.

EQUIPMENT: Nortek Signature 500 ADCP, SeaBirdSBE49 CTD, AirMar 120WX Weather Station

CURRENT STATE: unknown

INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES (INESC-TEC)

PLATFORM NAME: EGIM mod, UNDERWATER GLIDER #1; #2

DESCRIPTION: EGIM mod: EGIM, with custom built frame, COSTOF 2, 6 standard sensors, battery pack, WIFI modem. UNDERWATER GLIDER: Upgraded G2 Slocum, with automatic mission planning capabilities and offline navigation data correction (under development).

EQUIPMENT: EGIM: SBE 37 SeaBird CTD, Ocean Sonics Smart Hydrophone, Teledyne RDI 300 kHz Monitor ADCP, Aanderaa Oxygen Optode 4831DW, RBR Quartz 3 BPR bottom pressure recorder, WETLABS FLNTURTD 6731

UNDERWATER GLIDER #1 and #2: SeaBird CTD, SeaBird ECO Triplet, Aanderaa Oxygen Optode 4831

CURRENT STATE: EGIM: Tested in Madeira-Tore campaign (November 2021); COSTOF2 has been updated (May 2022)

UNDERWATER GLIDER #1: Tested in EMSO-PT Leg01 campaign (May 2021)

INSTITUTO PORTUGUÊS DO MAR E DA ATMOSFERA (IPMA)

PLATFORM NAME: EGIM

DESCRIPTION: Off the shelf EGIM, with a titanium frame, COSTOF 2, 6 standard sensors, battery pack, WIFI communication module.

EQUIPMENT: SBE 37 SeaBird CTD, Ocean Sonics Smart Hydrophone, Teledyne RDI 300 kHz Monitor ADCP, Aanderaa Oxygen Optode 4831DW, RBR Quartz 3 BPR bottom pressure recorder, WETLABS FLNTURTD 6731

CURRENT STATE: Pilot deployment June 2022 – ongoing

INSTITUTO SUPERIOR DE ENGENHARIA DO PORTO (ISEP)

PLATFORM NAME: TURTLE

DESCRIPTION: TURTLE is a hybrid lander, being capable of staying at the bottom of the sea for long periods of time, but also of autonomously relocating itself and surfacing for maintenance operations. It is also able to dive and ascend with high-energy efficiency, and its autonomous capabilities allow for reduced operational costs and flexibility.

EQUIPMENT: INESC-TEC Autonomous Robotic Deep Sea Lander

CURRENT STATE: unknown

INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO (IST)

PLATFORM NAME: N.A.

DESCRIPTION: UNDERWATER GLIDER: Based on an off the shelf field proven, very reliable Glider AUV, new software modules will be added to implement new navigation and control algorithms. These will extend the capabilities of the system regarding cooperation among autonomous robots, for example enabling the execution of missions with multiple glider AUVs and ASVs.

PRESSURE CHAMBER: Pressure chamber for testing equipment up to 700 bar (equiv. to 7000 m). Internal dimensions (max. size for equipment to be tested): diameter = 300 mm, length = 1600 mm.

ACOUSTIC COMMUNICATION SYSTEM: System for platform data transmission

EQUIPMENT: Slocum 1000 m G3, Pressure Chamber, Acoustic Communication System

CURRENT STATE: Slocum delivered in April 2022

LABORATÓRIO DE SISTEMAS E TECNOLOGIA SUBAQUÁTICA (LSTS) + INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO (IST)

PLATFORM NAME: APDR

DESCRIPTION: Autonomous Event-Driven Profiler and Data Retrieval System. Not fixed, not tethered

EQUIPMENT: AML – SmartX CTD

CURRENT STATE: unknown

UNIVERSIDADE DE AVEIRO (UA)

PLATFORM NAME: DEEP-SEA CAMERA + STROBE SYSTEM

DESCRIPTION: The DSC 24,000 Digital Still Camera is a 24.1 megapixel sensor, high-quality imaging for mooring, ROV, towed and autonomous applications. With a completely unmodified Nikon D7100 digital single-lens reflex camera (DSLR), the DSC 24,000 is able to utilize high quality Nikon DSLR lenses, while allowing for relatively inexpensive and easy exchange of the camera body and/or lens.

EQUIPMENT: Ocean Imaging Systems (OIS) - DSC 24.000

CURRENT STATE: Equipment with CCMAR

DATASET DESCRIPTION

EMSO-ERIC Iberian Margin aims at collecting long-time series of physical and biogeochemical parameters from the seafloor (subsurface moored platforms and instrumentation), water column (moored profiler) and sea surface. The raw data (as provided by the sensors) undergoes a first level of metadata processing and homogenization following naming, units and date format conventions (refer to Chpt. Data Treatment).

DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

DOCUMENTATION

Clear and detailed documentation during the data collection is key to writing comprehensive metadata to accompany the dataset. The documentation should include the basic five W's + H; WHO, WHERE, WHAT, WHEN, WHY and HOW and should be done during the collection process, so that no information is forgotten, and thus lost. Before a campaign a person responsible must be selected for documentation to avoid confusion in the field.

METADATA

Well-written metadata allows easy findability and accessibility to the dataset, which then can be used by fellow scientist or others. Global metadata describes the content of the dataset and should include a short description of the collection process, the location, time coverage, title, people involved, applied conventions and standards as well as data format and most importantly a license. Metadata describing variable parameters must state the variable name, unit and instrument. Please refer to **ANNEX 1** for the metadata catalogue of EMSO-ERIC Iberian Margin.

DATA TREATMENT

(META)DATA HARMONIZATION AND STANDARDIZATION

(Meta)data is harmonized accordingly to the EMSO-ERIC Metadata template, which is based on the following standards;

VOCABULARY AND METADATA ATTRIBUTES

SeaDataNet BODC VOCAB LIBRARY

- **P01** BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary
- **P06** BODC-approved data storage units
- **L05** SeaDataNet device categories

- **L22** SeaVoX Device Catalogue

COPERNICUS MARINE IN SITU TAC – PHYSICAL PARAMETER LIST

NetCDF CLIMATE AND FORECAST (CF) METADATA CONVENTIONS

FORMATTING

OceanSITES DATA FORMAT REFERENCE MANUAL

DATETIME ISO 8601

Dates are represented as **YYYY-MM-DD** e.g. the 27th January 2019 should be represented as; **2019-01-27**. Time is represented in Zulu Military Time (UTC) as **hh:mm:ss** e.g. 10.30 pm and 20 seconds should be represented as; **22:30:20Z**

For the moment data will be published unprocessed nor undergo any quality control, which will change in the future. Subsequently, an updated version of the data management plan will be published. Versioning is tracked via log-file, indicating the version date, changes made, and version number. Raw, versioned and final validated data and metadata is converted from native file formats into *.csv files (if not already in *.csv format) and thus can be read and edited by various commercial and freely available software such as Microsoft Excel, MATLAB, Python, and others. Validated data files are additionally converted into netCDF, *.nc, in order to link data to its associated metadata in one coherent file. Therefore, data is easy accessible and understandable for other users.

A DOI (Digital Object Identifier) will be assigned to the data and the corresponding metadata (yet to be established).

DATA STORAGE AND BACKUP

CENTRO DE CIÊNCIAS DO MAR (CCMAR)

Folders dependencies follow a layered naming based on EMSO facility code (IbMa-CVS), subsystem code (WW, EGIM), deployment year, deployment number (d01, d02, ..., dnn) and deployment date, datatype (metadata, data), dataset type (raw, edit, share) and format (binary, netCDF, csv).

Folder naming is done in capital letters and snake case.

Dependency example:

[drive_path]\IbMa_CVS\EGIM\YYYY\D01_YYYYMMDD\DATA\EDIT\NET_CDF

File naming follows subsystem code (WW, EGIM), deployment number (d01, d02, ..., dnn), deployment period, and version(v001, v002, ..., vnnn). Made changes are tracked in a log-text file, which are located

in the “dataset type” – directory. Instrument data (raw) is identified with the code “*_v000” and metadata with code “*_M”

File naming example:

[folder_path]\WW_d01_yyyymmdd_to_yyyymmdd_v001.csv

Other EMSO-ERIC Iberian Margin entities are advised to follow closely the folder dependencies and file naming standards of CCMAR in order to prevent data confusion and data loss. If a different naming convention is in place, it must be easily finable and understandable for others.

Long term data preservation (indefinite) is done in three independent storage locations, thus data loss is avoided, in case of unforeseen incidents. Firstly, data is stored with redundant drives at the CCMAR CETA computational infrastructure (1 TB capacity), housed in the UALG Datacenter Ed. 2 Campus de Gambelas. Secondly, on an external hard drive (1 TB capacity), which is stored at CCMAR, and thirdly, on a second external hard drive (1 TB capacity), which is kept by the Data Manager (Sarah A. Rautenbach, srautenbach@ualg.pt) and used for data processing.

Table 1. Summary of data types with corresponding formats and their storage location

LOCATION	STORAGE TYPE	DATA	FORMAT
CETA	Archive	Raw instrument data (compressed)	*.zip, *.csv
CETA	Archive	Versioning, validated dataset (shared)	*.csv, *.nc
CETA	Redundant 1	Raw instrument (compressed), versioning, validated dataset (shared)	*.zip, *.csv, *.nc
CETA	Redundant 2	Raw instrument (compressed), versioning, validated dataset (shared)	*.zip, *.csv, *.nc
HD 1 CCMAR	Backup 1	Raw instrument (compressed), versioning, validated dataset (shared)	*.zip, *.csv, *.nc
HD 2 CCMAR	Backup 2; work device	Raw instrument (compressed), versioning, validated dataset (shared)	*.zip, *.csv, *.nc

Raw instrument data will be compressed into *.zip format in order to save storage capacity. Validated data will be uploaded to **CCMAR ERDDAP** and eventually shared with other global data aggregators (yet to be defined).

Raw instrument data (*.zip, *.csv), versioning (*.csv) and the final processed version (*.nc) are stored for indefinite time. Validated data will be preserved at CCMAR ERDDAP and EMSO-ERIC data service, thus it can be openly accessed and (re)used by others. No data must be destroyed for legal or similar reasons, since no sensitive or personal data is collected nor preserved.

Responsibility for regular backups and maintenance of data and associated metadata integrity is assigned to the EMSO-ERIC Iberian Margin Data Manager Sarah A. Rautenbach (srautenbach@ualg.pt). CETA-server can only be accessed via ssh-key and password, which rights are

reserved to the EMSO-ERIC Iberian margin Data Manager. If access is needed, please contact the Data Manager for further details.

DATA SHARING

Validated data should be made publicly available as netCDF (*.nc) and comma-separated files (*.csv), with open-access at the data service platforms; **CCMAR ERDDAP**, **EMSO-ERIC DATA PORTALS**. The users can view a brief graphical presentation of the Iberian Margin Network of observatories and the recorded data, as well as download the datasets of interest. The access to the download services is free.

Data collected from EMSO-ERIC Iberian partners other than CCMAR should be aggregated by the Data Manager, who is responsible on making the data publicly available at the above described platforms. Therefore, the other partners are asked to share the validated data incl. metadata in netCDF format with the Data Manager. In case of difficulties in the conversion of the data into netCDF, please contact the Data Manager for support (srautenbach@ualg.pt).

ETHICAL AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

Data are product of EMSO-ERIC PT and are licensed with CC-BY. This license allows other users to adapt data according to their needs and share and redistribute that data free, even commercially under the condition that made changes are indicated and appropriate credit is given to the data owner.

Data of EMSO-ERIC Iberian Margin do not contain sensitive data.

LICENSE

CC-BY

DISTRIBUTION STATEMENT

These data follow the standards adopted by EMSO ERIC; they are public and free of charge. User assumes all risk for use of data. User must display citation in any publication or product using data. User must contact Lead PI prior to any commercial use of data.

CITATION

These data were collected by the EMSO-PT project (<http://emso-pt.pt/>) operated locally by Centre of Marine Sciences (<https://www.ccmар.ualg.pt/>) and made freely available by EMSO ERIC (<http://emso.eu/>)

ANNEX 1

EMSO-ERIC IBERIAN MARGIN METADATA CATALOGUE

GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES	VARIABLE ATTRIBUTES
date_created	long_name
conventions	standard_name
institution_edmo_code	units
geospatial_lat_min	comment
geospatial_lat_max	coordinates
geospatial_lon_min	ancillary_variables
geospatial_lon_max	sdn_parameter_name
geospatial_vertical_min	sdn_parameter_urn
geospatial_vertical_max	reference_scale
time_coverage_start	sdn_uom_name
time_coverage_end	sdn_uom_urn
update_interval	sdn_instrument_name
site_code	sdn_instrument_urn
emso_facility	sensor_manufacturer
source	sensor_model
platform_code	sensor_serial_number
wmo_platform_code	sensor_reference
data_type	sensor_identifier
format_version	sensor_mount
network	sensor_orientation
data_mode	
title	
summary	
keywords	
keywords_vocabulary	
project	
QC_indicator	
principal_investigator	
principal_investigator_email	
license	